

Synthesis of Benzopyrylium Compounds. Part I.

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It has been established by the authors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 599) in a preliminary note on the subject that coumarins condense with phenols to give benzopyrylium compounds when phosphorus oxychloride is used as condensing agent. The following compounds prepared by the new method have already been described :

(I) 2':4'-Dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride (from coumarin and dimethoxyresorcin).

(II) 2':4'-Dihydroxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride (from resorcin and coumarin).

(I)

(II)

The reaction has now been further extended. As one of us is not able to continue the work, the results so far obtained are published.

The following compounds have been prepared: 4'-Methoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride (from anisole and coumarin), 3':4'-dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride (from veratrol and coumarin), 4:7-dimethyl-3':4'-dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride (from dimethoxyveratrol and 4:7-dimethylcoumarin), 4:7-dimethyl-2':4'-dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride (from dimethylresorcin and 4:7-dimethylcoumarin).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The general method already described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) has been adopted. The mixture of phenol and coumarin in molecular proportions was heated on the water-bath with POCl_3 until the mass thickened. It was then treated with ice cold dry ether repeatedly to take away the unacted coumarin and phenol and finally dissolved in strong hydrochloric acid and from the solution the

benzopyrylium ferric chloride compound was precipitated by concentrated solution of FeCl_3 and crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

4'-Methoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride.—Dark red shining crystals, m.p. 125° (Found: Cl, 32.49; Fe, 12.8. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{FeCl}_4$ requires Cl, 32.64; Fe, 12.87 per cent).

3':4'-Dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride.—Red microcrystals, m.p. 192° . (Found: Cl, 30.42; Fe, 12.20. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{FeCl}_4$ requires Cl, 30.54; Fe, 12.04 per cent).

4:7-Dimethyl-3':4'-dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride.—Red microcrystals, m.p. 180° . (Found: Cl, 28.37; Fe, 11.53. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{FeCl}_4$ requires Cl, 28.80; Fe, 11.36 per cent).

4:7-Dimethyl-2':4'-dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride.—Dark violet powder, m.p. 150° . (Found: Cl, 29.14; Fe, 10.97. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{FeCl}_4$ requires Cl, 28.80; Fe, 11.36 per cent).

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